

LANGUAGE PROGRAMMING C++ BASED CODE::BLOCK IN TEMPARATURE UNIT CONVERSION

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ABSTRAK

Temperature is the cold heat of an object, if temperature of an object gets higher then will the object gets heat too. Energy that showed by temperature usually owned of the object. So the temperature becomes measuring instrument for climate and resource balance that is on earth by because of it high and low temperature is element very important for various research done by scientists. Tool for measuring temperature named a thermometer , which the thermometer itself divided become 4 that is thermometer Celsius, thermometer Reaumur, thermometer Fahrenheit and thermometer kelvin . to determine temperature scale system needed bottom reference point and top reference point. So that can concluded that calculation of temperature change become thing required for continuation of human civilization. Related with things these author make a simple temperature conversion proگرامing language with based codeblocks, which can make it easy for us to converting temperature unit without should using special technique.

Keyword : temperature , thermometer

1. PRELIMINARY

a) Background

The average energy level of the object can stated by temperature in unit of degrees Celsius , Fahrenheit , Reaumur , and Kelvin. The temperature itself divided into two, that is maximum temperature and minimum temperature because the temperature is measure of heat degrees of the object or the place. While tool measuring temperature named a thermometer , and often that used is mercury thermometer and alcohol.

Temperature is also included element very important in life on the world , especially for humans, animals, or plants . The living things in adapting with environment also determined by temperature.

b) Formulation of the problem

Based on the background above , then can be formulated a problem namely how to convert temperature unit from Celsius , to Reaumur, kelvin and Fahrenheit to make it easier to apply.

c) Purpose

To meet the semester final assignment algorithmic and programming courses.

d) Benefit

1. Can make it easier for us to convert temperature with simple way
2. Don't have to use looping technique or branching
3. Can use operation initialization

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Related research

There are several research related about the converting temperature unit using language programming C++ based codeblock , among others :

JIHAN PRATIWI “sejarah bahasa pemrograman C / C++ dan CodeBlocks”(2018)

From the result of the above research stated that the codeblock application that uses the GUI display is already available the executor of the application. Codeblock will make code writing easier and program running is also easier . this application is also free to use so there is no need to worry about licensing.

DWIANGGRIAWAN “Makalah temperatur suhu” (2014)

Research result that can be obtained namely on the Celsius scale , 0 degrees is the temperature at which water freezes and 100 degrees is the temperature boiling water. While on the Fahrenheit scale point at which water freezes from 32 degrees and boiling point is 212 degrees.

2.2 Theoretical basis

1. Conversion is a way to changing unit value to other units, and with not changing magnitude. This can be done with unit the same or different.
2. Temperature is the cold heat of an object , if temperature of an object gets higher then will the object gets heat too. Energy that showed by temperature usually owned of the object. While tool for measuring temperature named a thermometer , which the thermometer itself divided become 4 thermometer that is Celsius , Reaumur , Fahrenheit and kelvin. This Thermometer Celsius was discovered by Anders celcius a physicist from Sweden in the year 1701-1744. Thermometer Fahrenheit discovered by a scientist from German named Gabriel Daniel Fahrenheit in year 1686-1736. Thermometer Reaumur is scale given named and first proposed by Rene Antoine Ferchault de Reaumur in year 1731. In Europe the reamur scale widely used especially German and french. Thermometer scale kelvin itself is determined by a scientist from England, there is a minimum temperature in this world for the kelvin scale determined based on calculation.
3. Programming C++ is development from language C , developed by Dennis Ritchie in year 1970 in the Bong Labs. Language C++ itself made by Bjarne Stroustrup.
4. Temperature conversion is a way of changing scale to another , so for find out the conversion of a temperature is needed some comparison Celsius scale, Reaumur, Fahrenheit , and kelvin.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

Research stage as follows :

- a. Data Collecting
- b. Data processing
- c. Grouping
- d. Method used
- e. Testing
- f. Evaluation
- g. The results accurate

The method used in this research is language programming C++ based codeblock in convert temperature unit , this can make it easier the conversion of temperature units simply without using special techniques.

Temperature Celsius on can be converted to kelvin scale, Reaumur or Fahrenheit . to be able to the change from one temperature to another we use a predetermined formula. But don't rule out the possibility the convert can also be done from another scale, not only from Celsius scale. For example the thermometer scale X and Y will determined by the thermometer X with Xa

bottom fixed point and X_b upper fixed point . then thermometer Y with Y_b become bottom fixed point and Y_a become upper fixed point, the second thermometers above are temperature of the ice when melting and temperature of the water boils at a pressure of 1 atmosphere .

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

After done observation then comparison between temperature changes with interval of two fixed points each thermometer , can be obtained as follows :

$$\frac{T_x - X_b}{X_a - X_b} = \frac{T_y - Y_b}{Y_a - Y_b}$$

Information :

T_x = temperature on thermometer X

T_y = temperature on thermometer Y

X_a = upper fixed point on thermometer X

X_b = bottom fixed point on thermometer X

Y_a = upper fixed point on thermometer Y

Y_b = bottom fixed point on thermometer Y

5. DISCUSSION

A. Converting temperature manually

a. Converting temperature from Celsius to Reaumur

Formula : $R = 4/5 \times C$

Example : if its known Celsius temperature 20 , then the temperature of the Reaumur is..

$$R = 4/5 \times 20 = 16R$$

b. Converting temperature from Celsius to kelvin

Formula : $K = C + 237$

Example : if its known Celsius temperature 30 , then the temperature of the kelvin is...

$$K = 30 + 237 = 267 K$$

c. Converting temperature from Celsius to Fahrenheit

Formula : $F = 9/5 \times C + 32$

Example : if its known Celsius temperature 32 , then the temperature of the Fahrenheit is...

$$F = 9/5 \times 32 + 32 = 89,6 F$$

B. Converting temperature with language programming C++ based Codeblock

Based on the discussion above can be known how to convert temperature manually. As for how to convert with use language programming C++ based Codeblock.

Program language can be written as follows :

```
#include <iostream>

using namespace std;

int main()
{
    float suhuCel;
    cout << "          Program Konversi" << endl;
    cout << "          Suhu" << endl;
    cout << "-----" << endl;
    cout << "" << endl;
    cout << " Masukkan suhu dalam Celcius = " ;cin>>suhuCel;
    cout << "" << endl;
    cout << "* Suhu dalam Reamur = "<<suhuCel *4/5<<endl;
    cout << "* Suhu dalam Farenheit = " <<(suhuCel * 9/5)+32<<endl;
    cout << "* Suhu dalam Kelvin = "<<suhuCel + 273 <<endl;
    cout << "" << endl;
    cout << "-----" << endl;
    return 0;
}
```

The next program is run by pressing CTRL+F9 on the keyboard or click run on the taskbar.

Then will appear results program as shown below :

Select "C:\Users\DELL\Documents\pak andi\suhu\bin\Debug\suhu.exe"

```
Program Konversi
Suhu
-----
Masukkan suhu dalam Celcius = 32
* Suhu dalam Reamur = 25.6
* Suhu dalam Farenheit = 89.6
* Suhu dalam Kelvin = 305
-----
Process returned 0 (0x0)   execution time : 12.847 s
Press any key to continue.
```


6. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Results of the research above using data temperature on Saturday , 8 december 2018 by 32 degrees Celsius . Temperature that is previously converted to Fahrenheit , Reaumur and kelvin. Calculation the convert temperature using language programming C++ based codeblock can be improve accuracy in calculation and more effective and efficient use than those using manual methods. For suggestion a way the converting temperature unit with not manually, needed special expertise to little study language programming C++ based codeblock. So,never give up and keep spirit.

7. COVER

Research with the little 'LANGUAGE PROGRAMMING C++ BASED CODEBLOCK IN TEMPERATURE UNIT CONVERSION' finally can be resolved with existence of support from several parties . the author very realized existence a limitation in this research, so very expected there are criticisms and suggestions to perfect research.

Thank you.

8. LIST LIBRARY

1. Purwanti indah Tjahyani . 2017. Inovasi Alat Peraga belkonsu Dalam Pembelajaran Suhu Dan Perubahannya Di SMP Negeri 2 Blora. Artikel. Dikutip dari <https://jurnal.uns.ac.id>
2. Allex Sandra wilyan .2017.Contoh Program Konversi Suhu.Makalah.
3. Sandy Radja dkk.2014. Maklah Pemrograman Komputer Konversi Satuan Suhu. www.academia.edu
4. Prasetyo Andy. 2018. Pedoman Pembelajaran Algoritma Pemrograman Dasar. Purbaya E-Journal
5. <https://www.google.co.id/amp/fisikazone.com/suhu-dan-pengukurannya/amp/>
6. Jihan pratiwi.2018.sejarah bahasa pemrograman C / C++ dan CodeBlocks.blog
7. Dwianggriawan.2014.Makalah Temperatur Suhu.Makalah

9. ORIGINALITY STATEMENT

I declare with truthfully article that I made is results my own work and with this I'm fully responsible except for a few snippets which I have explained the source.

[Rizqi Meisani 2018.12.08]